

The technology is unsafe. The nuclear transfer technique that produced Dolly required 277 embryos, from which only one healthy and viable sheep was produced. The other fetuses were hideously deformed, and either died or were aborted. Moreover, we do not know the long term consequences of cloning [1].

Cloning is playing God. It is not merely intervention in the body's natural processes, but the creation of a new and wholly unnatural process of asexual reproduction. Philosophers and clerics of many faiths oppose human cloning. They caution that the failure to produce scientific reasons against the technology does not mean we should deny our strong instinctive revulsion [2].

Reproductive cloning injures the family. Single people will be able to produce offspring without a partner. Once born, the child will be denied the love of one parent, most probably the father. Several theologians have recognized that a child is a symbolic expression of the mutual love of its parents and their hope for the future. This sign of love is lost when a child's life begins in a laboratory.[3]

Many churches and secular organizations, including WHO, view reproductive cloning as contrary to human dignity [3].

Cloning will lead to eugenics. When people are able to clone themselves they will be able to choose the kind of person to be born. This seems uncomfortably close to the Nazi concept of breeding a race of Aryan superhumans, while eliminating those individuals whose characteristics they considered undesirable [4].

Cloning will lead to a diminished sense of identity and individuality for the resultant child. Instead of being considered as a unique individual, the child will be an exact copy of his parent and will be expected to share the same traits and interests. His life will no longer be his own. This is an unacceptable infringement of the liberty and autonomy that we grant to every human person. The confusion of the offspring is likely to be compounded by the fact that the "parent," from whom he is cloned, will be genetically his twin brother. There is no way of knowing how children will react to having such a confused genetic heritage [5].

Cloning will lead to a lack of diversity in the human population. The natural process of evolution will be halted, and humankind will be denied development [6].

Cloning treats children as commodities. Individuals will be able to have a child with desired characteristics as a symbol of status, rather than because they desire to conceive, love, and raise another human being [7].

Another suggestion has been that cloning could add to the number of options that might be offered to couples facing problems with infertility. But, a range of methods already exists for helping couples limited by infertility. For the most part, existing methods are affordable, readily available, and highly effective for those who try them. Very few people cannot be helped by existing methods of infertility treatment, and their lack, while sad, is not a tragedy. Couples who desire to conceive biological children and find they are unable, face real disappointment. Their disappointment can be profound, but only because it is sad, not because it is tragic.

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**DORIVOR ISMALOQDAN OLINADIGAN BIOLOGIK FAOL
MODDALARNI TIBBIYOTDA QO'LLASH**

**ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ В МЕДИЦИНЕ БИОЛОГИЧЕСКИ АКТИВНЫХ
ВЕЩЕСТВ, ПОЛУЧАЕМЫХ ИЗ ШПИНАТА ЛЕКАРСТВЕННОГО**

**MEDICAL USE OF BIOLOGICALLY ACTIVE SUBSTANCES DERIVED
FROM MEDICINAL SPINACH**

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Annotatsiya: *O'simlikning kimyoviy tarkibi murakkab va turlicha. Uning tarkibida uglevod, oqsil va moylardan tashqari, inson organizmi uchun foydali va muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan vitaminlardan A, E va K kabi biologik faol moddalar mavjudligi aniqlandi. Mana shu biologik faol moddalar sabab bir qancha kasalliklarni davolashda ishlatilishi aniqlandi; konyuktivit, anemiya, yurakning ishemik infarkti.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ismaloq, efir moyi, turli glikozidlar, alkaloidlar, oshlovchi moddalar, minerallar, biologik faol modda, moddalar almashinuvi.*

Аннотация: *Химический состав растения сложен и разнообразен. Установлено, что помимо углеводов, белков и жиров в его состав входят такие биологически активные вещества, как А, Е и К, а также витамины, полезные и важные для человеческого организма. Установлено, что эти биологически активные вещества используются при лечении ряда заболеваний, вызывающих; конъюнктивит, анемию, ишемический инфаркт сердца.*

Ключевые слова: *шпинат (Spinacia), эфирное масло, различные гликозиды, алкалоиды, добавки, минеральные вещества, биологически активные вещества, метаболизм.*

Annotation: *The chemical composition of the plant is complex and varied. In addition to carbohydrates, proteins and oils, it was found to contain biologically active substances, such as a, E and K, from vitamins that are beneficial and important for the human body. It was found that these biologically active substances are used in the treatment of several diseases caused by; conjunctivitis, anemia, ischemic heart attack.*

Keywords: *spinach, Essential Oil, various glycosides, alkaloids, additives, minerals, biologically active substance, metabolism.*

Organizmning normal hayotiy faoliyatini, uning ishlashi va sog'lig'ini belgilaydigan asosiy omillardan biri bu ovqatlanishdir. 19-asr oxiri va 20-asr boshlarida olib borilgan tadqiqotlar insonning ozuqaviy moddalarga bo'lgan ehtiyojlari haqidagi zamonaviy g'oyalarga asos yaratdi. Asosiy muhim oziq moddalar: aminokislotalar, yog 'kislotalari, vitaminlar va minerallar topildi.

Hozirgacha 20-asrning boshlarida ishlab chiqilgan, oziq-ovqat va parhezni baholashga mutanosib yondashishga asoslangan muvozanatli ovqatlanish nazariyasi muhim bo'lib qolmoqda. Ushbu nazariyaning asosiy mazmuni shundaki, ovqatlanish bu organizmning kimyoviy tarkibini saqlash va muvozanatlash jarayonidir. Ratsional muvozanatli oziqlanish turli xil oziq-ovqat tarkibiy qismlarining maqbul nisbatlarini nazarda tutadi, bu esa tanadagi plastik energiya va tartibga soluvchi moddalarni optimal iste'mol qilish bilan hayotiy faoliyatning normal darajasini ta'minlaydi. Adaptiv potentsialni saqlab qolish uchun oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarining bir qator makro va mikrokomponentlari (oqsillar, vitaminlar, kichik biologik faol birikmalar) zarur, ular ovqatlanish bilan ta'minlanishi kerak. Asosiy tarkibiy qismlardan (oqsillar, lipidlar yoki uglevodlar) birini dietadan uzoq muddat chiqarib tashlash qabul qilinishi mumkin emas.

Oziqlanishni ratsionalizatsiya qilish muammosining yechimi ba'zi oziq moddalar yetishmovchiligini qoplashga imkon beradigan, shuningdek organizmning turli organlari va tizimlariga zaif tartibga soluvchi ta'sir ko'rsatadigan dorilarni ishlab chiqarishga olib keldi. Ushbu dorilar biologik faol qo'shimchalar (BFQ) deb nomlanadi. Oziq-ovqat qo'shimchalaridan foydalanish quyidagi maqsadlarda oqlanadi:

- har bir aniq odam uchun uning fiziologik ehtiyojlari va energiya sarfini hisobga olgan holda ovqatlanishni ratsionalizatsiya qilish;
- dietaning kaloriya miqdorini kamaytirish;
- organizmning o'ziga xos bo'lmagan qarshiligini oshirish;
- metabolizmning yo'naltirilgan o'zgarishi - organizmga zaharli va begona moddalarning bog'lanishi va chiqarilishi;
- organizmning immunitet himoyasini oshirish;

- ichak mikroflorasini normallashtirish.

Hayvonlarni o'rganish shuni ko'rsatdiki, quritilgan ismaloq ekstraktlarining donador shakli ooferektomiya qilingan kalamushlarda osteoporozning rivojlanishi, suyak sinishi kabi kasalliklarni oldini olishda alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi – [1, p.698].

Asosan, biologik faol qo'shimchalar sog'lom odamlar tomonidan qo'llaniladi, kam hollarda - kasallikdan oldin, ular kasallik holatida ham foydalanishlari mumkin, ammo faqat asosiy terapiyaga qo'shimcha sifatida. Biologik faol moddalar o'simliklar hujayrasida to'xtovsiz ravishda biokimyoviy o'zgarishlar yuz berib turishi natijasida yuzaga keladi. Ular ma'lum vaqt va sharoitda turli o'zgarishlarga uchraydi. Buning natijasida ular boshqa birikmalarga aylanadi, murakkab molekulali moddalar sintezida ishtirok etadi yoki o'zidan energiya chiqarib, oddiy birikmalarga parchalanib ketadi. Eksperimental tadqiqotlar ismaloq barglari ekstraktlarining antikonvulsant xususiyatlarini aniqladi- [3, p.190]. Vitaminlarga boy va biologik faol moddalar tufayli ismaloqning tarkibi neyro-oziq-ovqat-ogohlantiruvchi oziq-ovqat deb ataladi neyrodejenerativ kasalliklar-Altsgeymer kasalligi va Parkinson –kabi kasalliklar uchun foydali tarkibga ega ekanligi aniqlandi [4, 108-bet].

Ismaloq ekstraktlari o'simta hujayralarining zararli radiatsiya nurlanish ta'siriga sezgirligini oshirishi aniqlandi [7, p.15006; 26, p.1455]. Flavanoidlar tufayli ismaloq barglari ishtahani bostiradi – [5, p.230]. Randomizatsiyalangan klinik tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, tilakoidlarni o'z ichiga olgan ismaloq barglarini iste'mol qilish, bu oziq – ovqat bilan tezroq to'yinganlikka olib keladi - [6, p.477].

Tadqiqot maqsadi. Mazkur ishning maqsadi virusli gepatit bilan kasallangan organizm uchun ozuqa tarkibini biologik faol moddalar bilan boyitish, dorivor ismaloq tarkibidagi biologik faol moddalarni o'rganish hamda minerallarga boy ozuqa tarkibini ishlab chiqishga doir ilmiy asoslangan tavsiyalar berishdan iborat.

Bugungi kunda etiologik omillarga, patogenezga va klinik ko'rinishga qarab turli xil jigar kasalliklarini farmakologik tuzatish uchun ko'plab dorilar mavjud. Ulardan ba'zilari turli xil asoratlarni va allergik reaksiyalarni keltirib chiqarishi mumkin, bu ulardan foydalanishni cheklaydi. So'nggi paytlarda tibbiyot amaliyoti

biologik faol moddalar va ularning komplekslarini biologik faol qo'shimchalar (BFQ) tarkibida oziq-ovqat mahsulotlariga yoki tibbiy va profilaktika ovqatlanishida ishlatiladigan oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarini boyitishga yo'naltirilgan yo'nalishni jadal rivojlantirmoqda. Gepatotrop ta'siriga ega bo'lgan bunday biologik faol moddalarga aminokislotalar va ularning hosilalari (leytsin, izoleysin, valin, arginin va boshqalar); peptidlar; vitaminlar (askorbin kislotasi, a-tokoferol, a-lipoik kislota va boshqalar); glikozidlar va boshqa antioksidantlar; fosfolipidlar; oligosaxaridlar; nuklein kislotalar; makro va mikroelementlar (selen, rux va boshqalar); organik kislotalar kiradi.

Bunday birikmalar yengil hazm bo'ladi, yurak-qon tomirlari, asab sistemasi, me'da-ichak yo'li, jigar, buyrak, nafas yo'llari, modda almashinuvining buzilishi va boshqa kasalliklarning oldini olish hamda davolashda keng qo'llaniladi.

Dorivor ismaloq (*Spinacia*) - sho'radoshlar (sho'ragullilar oilasi)ga mansub bir yoki ikki yillik o'simliklar turkumi, sabzavot ekini. Ismaloq ikki jinsli (aksariyat, ikki uyli), sovuqqa chidamli, tez yetiladigan o'simlik. AQSH, Kanada, Yevrosiyoda, jumladan, O'zbekistonda poliz Ismaloq (*S. Oleracea* L.) turi sabzavot sifatida o'stiriladi. Tarkibida karotin, vitamin B, B2, C, organik kislotalar bo'lib, xalq tabobatida siydik haydovchi dori sifatida hamda kamqonlik, raxit kasalliklariga qo'llaniladi. Bargidan gidrolizlab olingan maxsus oqsil modda meditsinada me'da osti bezi faoliyatini kuchaytiruvchi vosita sifatida ishlatiladi, barglari bahorda, vitaminlarga boy.

Bugungi kunda dorivor o'simliklardan biologik faol moddalarni ajratib olishning quyidagi usullari mavjud:

- Kimyoviy usulda ajratib olish
- Kombinatsiyalangan yoki fermentativ usulda ajratib olish
- Mikrobiologik usulda ajratib olish

Tadqiqot natijalari: Tajribalar natijasi shuni ko'rsatadiki, biologik faol moddalar ayniqsa, ismaloq- *Spinacia* (1-жадвал), ildiz, barg hamda poyasidan olinadigan dorivor moddalar kasallangan organizmning ovqat tarkibiga qo'shib berilsa bir qancha yaxshi tomonga o'zgarish borligini ko'rish mumkin.

Ismaloq barglari yashil sabzavot sifatida iste'mol qilinganda tanaga keng spektrda foydali ta'sir ko'rsatadi:

- yuqori qon bosimini barqarorlashtiradi;
- qon yo'qotishdan keyin yoki anemiyada qonning xususiyatlarini tiklaydi;
- markaziy asab tizimi va kognitiv funktsiyalarni yaxshilaydi;
- jigar faoliyatini normallashtiradi va xoleretik xususiyatlarga ega;
- qondagi shakar va xolesterin miqdorini pasaytiradi;
- reaktiv kislorod turlarini o'zlashtiradi va antioksidant faollikka ega;
- yallig'lanishga qarshi ta'sirga ega;
- immunitetni faollashtiradi;

miya hujayralarida metabolik jarayonlarni yaxshilaydi va Altsgeymer kasalligining rivojlanishiga to'sqinlik qiladi.

1-Жадвал.

Dorivor ismaloq tarkibidagi biologik faol moddalar

№	Biologik faol moddalar	100 gr	№	Biologik faol moddalar	100 gr
1.	Magniy	82 mg	6.	Natriy	24 mg
2.	Kalsiy	106 mg	7.	Xolin	2 mg
3.	Kaliy	774 mg	8.	Vitamin A	750 mkg
4.	Fosfor	83 mg	9.	Vitamin E	2,5 mg
5.	Temir	13,5 mg	10.	Vitamin K	483 mkg

Ismaloqni o'z ichiga olgan biologik faol moddalar ba'zi joylarda saraton xavfini kamaytiradi. Ular diabet va ateroskleroz rivojlanishining oldini olishga xizmat qiladi. Ushbu o'simlikning barglarini har kuni uzoq vaqt davomida iste'mol qilish mashqlar paytida mushaklarning kuchlanishini va shikastlanishini kamaytiradi.

Amaldagi eksperimentlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, ovqat tarkibini biologik faol moddalar bilan boyitish zararlarga hujayralarini qayta tiklash, organizm uchun immunitet hamda kuch bo'ladi. O'simliklardan olinadigan biologik faol moddalar sintetik usulda olinadigan biologik faol moddalarga qaraganda ancha yuqori faollikka ega bo'lib, bu moddalar tirik organizmda yaxshi so'rilish hamda tez ta'sir qilish xususiyatiga egadir. Ayniqsa, o'simliklardan olinadigan flavanoidlar jigar